

Legal Protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers in Badung Regency

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ABSTRACT: The increasingly difficult competition in the world of work in Indonesia causes many prospective workers to choose to work abroad as Indonesian Migrant Workers. The role of the government with regard to employment is not only as a policy maker, the Government can also act as a supervisor, controller and provide legal protection for migrant workers. The formulation of the problems in this study are: 1) How is the Badung Regency government policy in the placement of Indonesian Migrant Workers abroad? 2) How is the protection of Krama Badung Indonesian Migrant Workers abroad? The type of research used is empirical juridical research by examining and collecting primary data that has been obtained through direct observation. The results of this study indicate that the Badung Regency Government's policy on the placement of migrant workers abroad is based on the Bali Province Governor Regulation No. 12 of 2021 concerning the Protection System of Krama Bali Indonesian Migrant Workers and Law No. 18 of 2017 concerning the Protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers. Because the Badung Regency Government does not specifically regulate PMI, while the Badung Regency Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2021 only regulates the Implementation of Employment Services. The protection of Krama Badung Indonesian Migrant Workers is implemented in accordance with Bali Governor Regulation No. 12 of 2021 concerning the Protection System of Krama Bali Indonesian Migrant Workers emphasizing protection based on local wisdom.

KEYWORDS: Legal Protection, Workers, Indonesian Migrant, Badung Regency.

I. INTRODUCTION

Employment in Indonesia is still dominated by a shortage of job opportunities, as job growth does not keep pace with the increasing labor force. The increasingly fierce job competition has also driven many job seekers to choose to work abroad. As a result, the number of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) continues to rise, prompting the government to facilitate their deployment as a measure to reduce unemployment. According to Article 1 point 2 of Law No. 18 of 2017, Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) are Indonesian citizens who work abroad for a certain period of time in exchange for wages. The high interest in becoming a PMI benefits the country by helping to reduce unemployment and increase foreign exchange earnings. However, despite being referred to as "foreign exchange heroes," many PMIs still face a lack of attention from the state. This gives rise to various labor issues, particularly those related to legal protection, wages, justice, welfare, labor disputes and their resolution, as well as suboptimal oversight and regulation (Muhammad Junaidi 2024).

As part of national economic development, the government has established a legal policy for labor protection through Law Number 13 of 2003 concerning Manpower. According to Article 1 paragraph (2) of the law, labor refers to any person who is capable of working to produce goods and/or services, either for personal needs or for the community. Thus, anyone who is capable of working falls within the category of labor. In the context of national development, labor plays a crucial role both as a subject and as an objective of development. Therefore, the contribution of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMIs) to the national economy must be recognized through fair and humane treatment, as well as respect for their human rights. Considering that labor development is an essential component of national development and encompasses various aspects, comprehensive regulation is needed including human resource development, increased labor productivity and competitiveness, expansion of employment opportunities, job placement services, and the development of industrial relations (Asri Wijayanti 2016).

The placement of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMIs) abroad constitutes the fulfillment of a constitutional right, as every citizen has the right to equal opportunity for employment. This right to work is guaranteed under Article 27 paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, which states that every citizen has the right to employment and a decent living. In

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addition, Article 28D paragraph (2) affirms that every person has the right to work and to receive fair and proper treatment and compensation in employment relationships. These two articles reflect the state's commitment to protecting workers' rights. In the context of labor, workers are generally seen as being in a weaker position compared to employers in employment relationships, both socially and economically. Therefore, the state must intervene to provide greater protection through fair labor regulations that favor workers, in accordance with the principles of international labor law (I Nyoman Putu Budiarta 2016).

Article 5 of Law No. 13 of 2003 on Manpower states that every worker has the same opportunity without discrimination to obtain employment. This means that everyone has the right to decent work and livelihood regardless of gender, race, ethnicity, religion, or any other form of discrimination. The right to work is part of human rights in the fields of economics, social affairs, and culture. Labor protection through legislation aims to guarantee workers' fundamental rights and ensure equal treatment in order to achieve welfare. In the context of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMIs), Law No. 18 of 2017 was enacted to protect them from human trafficking, slavery, forced labor, violence, abuse of power, and other actions that violate human dignity and human rights (Solechan, Tri Rahayu Utami 2020).

Data from the Department of Manpower and Energy and Mineral Resources (Disnaker ESDM) of Bali Province shows that the number of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMIs) from Bali has continued to increase over the past three years. In 2022, the number of PMIs from Bali was recorded at 8,343 people, rising to 9,244 in 2023, and increasing again to 9,599 in 2024. Meanwhile, according to data from BP3MI, Bali Province consistently ranked fourth as the region with the highest number of migrant worker deployments abroad during the 2021–2022 period (Ni Kadek Yunita Dewi 2024). Bali Province has significant potential in the tourism sector, which also drives the availability of competent human resources in this field. In accordance with Article 1 point 8 of Governor Regulation Number 12 of 2021, *Pekerja Migran Indonesia Krama Bali* refers to Indonesian citizens residing in Bali as stated on their identity card (KTP) who work abroad for wages. PMIs from Krama Bali play a significant role in development, particularly at the regional level. One of the areas that contributes greatly to the tourism sector in Bali is Badung Regency, which is also an important source of migrant labor (Ni Komang Laba Swastami Yanti 2022).

However, it cannot be denied that Krama Bali from Badung Regency who register as Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMIs) also face various challenges, including cases of fraud. One prominent case occurred in 2022, involving 101 prospective PMIs students of the Infinity Training Centre (LKP and LPK) on Jalan Raya Sempidi, Badung Regency who fell victim to embezzlement and fraud by PT. Tulus Widodo Putra and PT. Dinasty Insan Mandiri, both based in Tangerang. These two companies had promised overseas job placements on the condition that each individual paid tens of millions of rupiah. However, despite the agreements made, the prospective PMIs were never deployed. This case reflects the low level of public understanding regarding official PMI placement procedures and the importance of verifying the legality of placement companies. Therefore, the active role of local governments especially the Department of Manpower is essential in regulating, supervising, and guiding the PMI placement process to prevent similar fraud cases in the future.

Amid the rise in fraud cases targeting Prospective Indonesian Migrant Workers (CPMI), the Badung Regency Government, through the Department of Industry and Manpower, needs to take concrete protective measures. One such measure is active involvement in the administrative verification process of CPMIs to prevent illegal practices. In addition, it is essential to provide clear education and information regarding the official procedures for becoming a PMI, including encouraging CPMIs to follow procedural deployment by completing the required documents and cooperating with officially licensed Indonesian Migrant Worker Placement Companies (P3MI). These efforts must also be supported by the establishment or strengthening of labor regulations at the regional level to address existing issues. Many problems faced by CPMIs/PMIs stem from a lack of understanding of placement procedures and vulnerability to persuasion and false promises such as offers of high salaries and quick processing which are often exploited by irresponsible parties. Therefore, improving labor literacy and enforcing stricter supervision are crucial steps in preventing the recurrence of such cases (Dewi Asri Puanandini 2020).

The role of the government in employment extends beyond policymaking; it also includes functions as a supervisor, regulator, and legal protector of migrant workers. The strong involvement of the state in labor affairs reflects Indonesia's corporatist labor law model. Government intervention in employment relationships between workers and employers is regulated under the Manpower Law, in which the government is positioned as one of the actors in the production process. This indicates that, in order to establish a harmonious, balanced, and equitable employment relationship between workers and employers, the government plays an active role in regulating and overseeing the implementation of such relationships (Khairani 2016).

Supervision of the implementation of labor laws is essential to ensure the fulfillment of workers' normative rights, which positively contributes to national stability and fosters legal compliance among both workers and employers. Therefore, the government is expected to optimally perform its role as a regulator in order to create a harmonious employment relationship. However, in reality, the fulfillment of workers' normative rights in Indonesia remains less than ideal due to a gap between the

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written law (law in the books) and its actual implementation in the field (law in action). This reflects the government's suboptimal performance in labor law enforcement and oversight (Arifuddin Muda Harahap 2023).

According to Government Regulation No. 4 of 2014, which refers to Law No. 34 of 2009, the placement of Indonesian workers abroad is carried out by both the government and the private sector. Meanwhile, Article 41 of Law No. 18 of 2017 emphasizes that the district/city governments are responsible for regulating, supervising, and facilitating the placement process of migrant workers. Article 1 paragraph 12 of Law No. 13 of 2003 states that the purpose of job placement is to match workers with employers in order to ensure alignment between the workers' abilities and the employers' needs. In the context of labor law, legal protection also covers the pre-placement or deployment stage that is, the period before the employment relationship begins which is a critical aspect of ensuring workers' rights (Asri Wijayanti 2009).

The Badung Regency Government has demonstrated its commitment to protecting local workers through Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2022 on the Administration of Employment Services. Under this regulation, the local government has the authority to conduct job-matching services, issue licenses to private labor placement agencies, and provide Job Seeker Information (IPK) services as well as job position data at the regional level. This affirms the active role of local governments in coordinating, synergizing, and evaluating the performance of labor-related stakeholders to ensure that the placement process of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMIs) in Badung is carried out in accordance with the regulations and involves legally licensed PMI placement companies (P3MI).

In accordance with the mandate of Law No. 18 of 2017 on the Protection and Placement of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMIs), regional regulations are needed as a legal foundation not only to ensure the protection of PMIs but also to strengthen the service functions of local governments. This law particularly Article 41 emphasizes that district and city governments serve as the frontline in protecting PMIs from their respective regions. Administrative protection from local governments can be realized through the establishment of regional regulations at the provincial, district/city, and even village levels. One concrete implementation of this policy is the establishment of the One-Stop Integrated Service (LTSA), which aims to provide more effective and integrated services for PMIs.

Based on the above background, it is important to conduct further research on the policies of the Badung Regency Government regarding the placement of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMIs) abroad and the protection of Krama Badung PMIs working overseas. This study aims to analyze the policies of the Badung Regency Government concerning the placement of PMIs originating from Badung who work abroad, as well as to examine the protection mechanisms for Krama Badung PMIs abroad.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The research method used is empirical legal research. This type of approach is employed to obtain information related to the issue being studied. The approaches used include the statutory approach, the conceptual approach, the sociological approach, and the comparative approach.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. The Policy of The Badung Regency Government on the Placement of Indonesian Migrant Workers Abroad

Regarding the placement of workers abroad, the Badung Regency Government previously enacted Regional Regulation (Perda) No. 8 of 2014 on Employment Services. However, since it was no longer relevant to current conditions, this regulation was replaced by Perda No. 10 of 2022. The issuance of this new regulation aligns with Fredrich's policy theory, which states that policy is a proposed course of action in a specific context that takes into account constraints and opportunities to achieve goals, and its success depends on implementation by various stakeholders (M. Solly Lubis 2007).

Based on Badung Regency Regional Regulation (Perda) No. 10 of 2022, the local government holds the authority to provide employment placement services, including job referral services, licensing of private employment agencies, and labor market information (IPK) management. This authority is further detailed in Article 23, which outlines responsibilities such as providing job referral services covering labor market information, job counseling, and job intermediation as well as human resource development at the sub-district level. In line with Minister of Manpower Regulation No. 9 of 2019, the provision of information regarding the placement of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) must include labor market conditions, placement procedures, and working conditions abroad. This information can be provided online or offline by the Integrated Service Center for Migrant Worker Placement (LTSA), the Regency/Municipal Manpower Office, village governments, or through job fairs. This regional regulation is also harmonized with Bali Governor Regulation No. 12 of 2021, under which the procedure for PMI placement in Badung begins with job seeker registration to obtain the AK-1 card, followed by the issuance of the Prospective Migrant Worker (CPMI) ID and passport recommendation by the Department of Industry and Manpower.

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The Department of Industry and Manpower of Badung Regency is only authorized to provide recommendations to placement companies (P3MI) that hold permits and job orders from foreign employers. The recruitment process for Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) is carried out by P3MI in coordination with the Badung Industry and Manpower Office (Disperinaker Badung). The Provincial Government of Bali regulates the protection of PMIs originating from Bali through Governor Regulation No. 12 of 2021, which mandates the use of the Sisnaker Krama Bali online system. Prospective PMIs (CPMI) must register and update their data in this system to facilitate services and address future issues. This regulation also requires P3MI to:

- a) Report the placement and return of PMIs online,
- b) Possess a SIP3MI and establish a branch office in Bali if they are based outside the region,
- c) Update placement data and documents in the Sisnaker system,
- d) Involve PMIs in pre-departure orientation, and
- e) Be responsible for resolving PMI-related issues.

The Provincial Government is also responsible for developing and managing Sisnaker as a data system for Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI), in collaboration with relevant agencies. This system serves as the basis for formulating labor policies. The policies established by the Provincial Government of Bali and the Regency Government of Badung reflect that every regulation is essentially rooted in human interests. This aligns with the perspective of Satjipto Rahardjo, who emphasized that law should be grounded in the principle that it exists to serve humanity. Therefore, the quality of law is determined by the extent to which it can realize the welfare and happiness of society as its primary objective. (I Nyoman Putu Budiarta 2018).

The policies issued by the Regency Government of Badung can be reviewed through the theory of authority. In general, authority is derived through three mechanisms:

- 1) Attribution, which refers to the direct granting of authority by the legislator to a government institution, and this authority is inherently attached to the position.
- 2) Delegation, which is the transfer of authority from one government organ to another, whereby the authority is fully transferred.
- 3) Mandate, which refers to the delegation of authority from a superior to a subordinate, where the responsibility remains with the grantor of the mandate.

The employment services provided by the Department of Industry and Manpower of Badung Regency include the provision of Labor Market Information (IPK), job counseling, and job placement intermediation. In the implementation of Indonesian Migrant Worker (PMI) placement procedures, the IPK services are tailored to the job orders submitted by licensed placement companies (P3MI). Good coordination between the Department and P3MI facilitates Prospective PMIs (CPMI) in accessing employment opportunities both domestically and abroad. Referring to Law No. 18 of 2017 on the Protection of PMIs and Badung Regency Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2022, particularly Article 24, it is emphasized that every worker has the right and equal opportunity to obtain employment fairly, transparently, and in accordance with their individual capabilities and potential. Labor placement must also uphold the principles of fairness, legal protection, and equal opportunity, aligned with national and regional needs. With the rapid growth of employment opportunities, especially overseas, it is essential for local governments to actively disseminate information about job opportunities to the public.

Article 1 point 33 of Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2022 concerning employment services defines Labor Market Information (IPK) as data on labor demand and supply, both domestically and abroad. The local government is authorized to manage IPK, including providing job-related information to job seekers and employers, and disseminating it within Badung Regency. This authority is both a right and obligation granted through legislation, as explained by Bagir Manan, and may be acquired through attribution, delegation, or mandate. In this context, the local government acts as the executor of employment affairs.

In the placement process of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI), one of the crucial initial stages is the provision of information. According to Minister of Manpower Regulation No. 9 of 2019, labor market information includes job vacancies, types of positions, job requirements, placement procedures, and working conditions abroad. Meanwhile, Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2022 stipulates that the Head of the Department is responsible for developing and managing an electronic Labor Information System. This system encompasses the comprehensive and continuous collection and dissemination of information, covering general employment data, training, labor placement, as well as industrial relations and worker protection. The technical provisions of this system will be further regulated through a Regent Regulation.

The Manpower Office of Badung Regency carries out the registration process for Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) in accordance with Minister of Manpower Regulation No. 9 of 2019 and Bali Governor Regulation No. 12 of 2021 on the protection of Krama Bali PMIs. The process is conducted online through the website siapkerja.kemnaker.go.id. One of the Office's roles is to check the completeness of administrative documents. Once all requirements are fulfilled, the Office will verify the data and confirm

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it with the agency, which will then submit a request for verification of the Placement Agreement. If all these steps have been completed, the Prospective PMI (CPMI) is declared procedurally and safely ready for departure..

The legal basis for drafting the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for AK/1 services in Badung Regency includes Law No. 13 of 2003 on Manpower, Minister of Manpower Regulation No. 39 of 2016, Badung Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2022, and Regent Regulation No. 43 of 2013 concerning the SOP formulation mechanism. AK/1, or the Job Seeker Identification Card, is one of the requirements for prospective Indonesian Migrant Workers (CPMI). The service is conducted in person, beginning with taking a queue number and submitting documents such as photocopies of the ID card (KTP), latest diploma, birth certificate, passport-sized photo, and other supporting documents. If the documents are complete, the officer conducts an interview regarding the applicant's interests and objectives, then verifies the data through the siapkerja.kemnaker.go.id website before printing the AK/1 card. Once printed and signed by the applicant, the card is checked and validated by an authorized official, then handed over to the applicant.

In the recruitment and placement process of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI), in addition to Badung Regency Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2022, the Regency Government of Badung, through the Department of Industry and Manpower, has also established a Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) for the Verification Service of Prospective PMIs related to the issuance of passport recommendation letters. This SOP is formulated based on Law No. 18 of 2017, BNP2TKI Regulation No. PER.30/KA/XII/2013, and Regent Regulation No. 43 of 2013. Its purpose is to ensure that the issuance of the CPMI ID is conducted on time and in accordance with established standards. Before the ID can be printed, the CPMI must complete all required documents, which will be verified by the officer to determine eligibility and to prevent illegal placement or fraud.

The creation of the CPMI ID is carried out online via the website <https://siapkerja.kemnaker.go.id>. However, applicants are still required to visit the Department of Industry and Manpower (Disperinaker) of Badung Regency to take a queue number and submit their application documents when called by the officer. The required documents include various photocopies, such as: a referral letter and SIP from the agency, ID card (KTP), family card (KK), latest diploma, AK/1 card, birth certificate, placement agreement, family consent letter acknowledged by the village head or urban ward chief, employment contract, seaman's book (if applicable), passport, marriage certificate, and passport-sized photo. Once the documents are verified and declared complete, further examination is conducted by a supervising officer. If all requirements are met, data verification is carried out, and the CPMI ID is issued to the applicant for use in the employment placement process.

The Regency Government of Badung facilitates Prospective Indonesian Migrant Workers (CPMI) through the SOP for Passport Recommendation Services, which regulates the workflow and administrative requirements. This SOP is based on Law No. 13 of 2003, Minister of Law and Human Rights Regulation No. 8 of 2014, and Regent Regulation No. 43 of 2013. Passport recommendation requirements are categorized into three types: self-application, through an agency/P3MI, and through a company. Once the applicant submits the required documents, the officer will verify their completeness. If the documents meet the requirements, the data will be entered into the Disperinaker E-Archive system and processed for electronic approval. Overall, the SOPs for AK/1 services, CPMI ID issuance, and passport recommendations have been designed systematically, with clearly defined workflows, requirements, and responsible personnel serving as a clear guide for CPMIs in handling administrative procedures before working abroad.

Badung Regency Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2022 on employment services reflects the application of Jeremy Bentham's theory of legal utility, which asserts that the purpose of law is to achieve the greatest happiness for the greatest number of people (Ibnu Artadi 2006). Law not only guarantees the public interest, but also balances individual interests in order to achieve justice that is acceptable to the broader society. In this context, government policies are designed to provide benefits and improve public welfare, particularly by facilitating access to employment services. In relation to Notonegoro's theory of justice, justice is realized when it aligns with the prevailing legal norms, where every citizen, including Prospective Indonesian Migrant Workers (CPMI), has the right to equal service and fair opportunities in gaining employment. (Awan Abdoellah 2016).

B. Protection for Indonesian Migrant Workers

Article 7 of Law No. 18 of 2017 stipulates that protection for Prospective Indonesian Migrant Workers (CPMI) and Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) covers three stages: before, during, and after employment.

- 1) Pre-employment protection includes administrative aspects such as the completeness of documents and the establishment of employment terms, as well as technical protection, which covers counseling, job training, social security, one-stop placement services, and supervision and guidance.
- 2) Protection during employment includes data registration by overseas officials, monitoring of working conditions, legal assistance, consular services, and facilitation of repatriation.

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- 3) Post-employment protection covers return to the place of origin, fulfillment of pending rights, assistance for sick or deceased PMIs, as well as rehabilitation and empowerment for PMIs and their families.

The protection efforts for Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) carried out by the Regency Government of Badung align with Philipus M. Hadjon's theory of legal protection, which states that the law for the people consists of two main aspects:

- 1) Preventive legal protection, which is a form of protection where the public is given the opportunity to express objections or opinions before a government decision becomes final;
- 2) Repressive legal protection, which refers to protection aimed at the resolution of disputes, usually after a government decision has been made or a legal issue has arisen.

Legal protection for Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) includes preventive measures through clear placement procedures and public outreach, enabling the community to choose officially licensed and registered placement companies (P3MI). The main goal is to ensure the rights and obligations of PMIs and safeguard their well-being while working abroad. In cases where rights violations occur, PMIs are also entitled to legal assistance. As the agency responsible for labor affairs, the Department of Industry and Manpower of Badung Regency enacted Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2022 to protect workers, guarantee fundamental rights, and prevent discrimination while still considering the dynamics of the business sector. This aligns with Article 33 of Law No. 18 of 2017, which mandates that the protection of PMIs before, during, and after employment must be carried out by both the central and regional governments in accordance with applicable legal provisions.

The Regency Government of Badung provides protection to Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) from the registration stage through to departure. In accordance with Law No. 18 of 2017, local governments play an important role in serving and protecting PMIs in their respective regions. Based on an interview with I Made Reta, Functional Officer for Job Placement at the Badung Manpower Office (Disperinaker Badung), although there is no specific regional regulation (perda) on PMIs yet, technical policies have been adjusted to align with Bali Governor Regulation No. 12 of 2021. The former Regional Regulation No. 8 of 2014 has been replaced by Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2022 to harmonize with national regulations and support an online-based system. Online services have already been implemented, but they remain suboptimal, as many members of the public still do not fully understand the procedures. In fact, this system is designed to simplify data entry and ensure that CPIMs are officially registered to receive clear legal protection. Unfortunately, many CPIMs still choose to go through non-procedural (unofficial) channels. To address this issue, the Badung Regency Government is making efforts to disseminate information both through the online system and via public outreach (socialization). At present, socialization programs are not yet conducted on a regular schedule, but moving forward, efforts will be made to ensure that information is delivered consistently and in coordination with the central government and other relevant agencies.

The Regency Government of Badung remains committed to improving the quality of employment services, including by enhancing the online system currently implemented through Sisnaker. Although this system has proven to be relatively effective, many Prospective Indonesian Migrant Workers (CPMI) still do not understand the process flow, highlighting the need for further public outreach (socialization) so that government policies especially at the regional level can be properly understood and accepted by the community. Public interest in Badung to work as PMIs remains lower than in other regencies in Bali. This is largely due to a lack of understanding regarding registration procedures and the limited availability of skill certifications. Many CPIMs are only aware of the destination country, type of job, and salary, but are unfamiliar with the official registration process. As a result, many choose to go through agents or P3MI without verifying their legality often leading to cases of fraud or exploitation..

The high number of complaints highlights the need for the active role of the government, particularly the Badung Manpower Office (Disperinaker Badung), in providing information and protection to Prospective Indonesian Migrant Workers (CPMI). Disperinaker continues to promote public outreach and monitoring of P3MI activities. One concrete example of this effort was a collaborative event in March 2025 at LPK PPLP Dhyana Pura, Dalung, which involved various stakeholders including the Bali Provincial Manpower Office, Disperinaker Badung, BP3MI Bali, and Bank BPD Bali. During the event, BP3MI Bali delivered a presentation titled "Safe and Procedural Overseas Employment." Overall, the Badung Regency Government continues to strive for procedural placement services for PMIs in line with national regulations and to foster collaboration with multiple parties to ensure optimal protection for CPIMs from Badung.

Legal protection for Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) before departure begins with proper data collection and documentation prior to placement. The Badung Manpower Office (Disperinaker Badung) also coordinates with the provincial government and BP3MI to address various challenges that PMIs may face while working abroad. This inter-agency collaboration is essential to ensure that the placement process complies with regulations and contributes positively to the workers' welfare. One concrete step taken by the Badung Regency Government is its active participation in joint outreach activities with the Bali Provincial Government and BP3MI, targeting Vocational Training Institutions (LPK) in the Badung area. The aim is to enhance public understanding especially among skilled individuals of the legal procedures for PMI placement, while also preventing data or

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document manipulation. Disperinaker Badung continues to strengthen coordination with relevant agencies to suppress the practice of non-procedural placement.

Several fraud cases highlight the importance of strict supervision. For example, a case in 2021 involving PT. DIM in Kerobokan, where the company promised cruise ship jobs and collected money from CPIMs, even though it lacked official authorization as required by Minister of Transportation Regulation No. 84 of 2013 and Law No. 18 of 2017. Another case occurred in 2022, involving PT. MAG Diamond, which deceived CPIMs from Badung by promising employment in Japan but never followed through with deployment, despite having collected upfront fees. In response to the increasing number of fraud cases involving unauthorized P3MI actors in Badung Regency, the Badung Manpower Office (Disperinaker Badung) has taken preventive action by summoning relevant parties such as Vocational Training Institutions (LPK), Professional Certification Bodies, and P3MI operating in the region. As the supervisory authority over P3MI, Disperinaker is committed to taking firmer measures, including recommending license revocation to the central government if any violations or fraud against CPIMs are proven.

Protection for Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) during employment abroad includes efforts to safeguard both the rights of PMIs and their families. According to Bali Governor Regulation No. 12 of 2021, Krama Bali PMIs are entitled to professional, nondiscriminatory services, freedom of worship, wages in accordance with their contracts, legal assistance, access to communication, ownership of travel documents, freedom of association, and access to placement and employment contracts. Article 10 paragraph (3) of the regulation mandates that protection be carried out through coordination among the provincial government, regency/municipal governments, and relevant institutions. This serves as the basis for the Badung Regency Government in providing protection to PMIs during their employment abroad, including consultation services related to documents, wages, and employment contracts. As part of its supervisory strategy, the Badung Regency Government promotes transparency and PMI participation by providing channels to report violations or issues encountered while working. This enables quick and responsive handling of any rights violations. Inter-agency collaboration is also being continuously strengthened to reinforce protection throughout the duration of employment in the destination countries.

Post-employment protection for Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) includes assistance from the time they return to Indonesia until they arrive in their home regions, as well as support to help them reintegrate as productive workers. According to Bali Governor Regulation No. 12 of 2021, post-employment protection includes repatriation to their place of origin, settlement of outstanding entitlements, assistance for PMIs who are ill or deceased, and social rehabilitation and empowerment. The Regency Government of Badung carries out these protections through coordination with the central government and relevant institutions. A concrete example is the repatriation of the remains of a PMI from Canggu Village, I Nyoman Sudiana, who passed away in Japan in December 2024. The Badung Manpower Office (Disperinaker Badung) collaborated with the Indonesian Embassy in Tokyo and the Balinese community in Japan to manage the administrative procedures and the repatriation process. However, the process faced challenges due to the deceased's overstay status and nonprocedural employment. This case serves as an important lesson for the public to follow official procedures when registering as a PMI. Having a legal status facilitates government efforts in data management and in providing legal protection in emergency situations.

District and municipal-level manpower offices serve as a key point of access for PMIs, reflecting the local government's commitment to addressing the various issues faced by PMIs before, during, and after employment. Although demand for labor from abroad is relatively high, the number of PMIs from Badung Regency remains low. One of the main reasons is that many prospective PMIs (CPMI) still choose non-procedural channels, due to a lack of understanding regarding safe and legal overseas placement procedures. Data shows that the number of PMIs from Badung is lower than that of other regencies in Bali. This is due to limited access to information about overseas labor markets, as well as a lack of professional certifications among prospective workers, which makes them ineligible for certain job positions. As a result, some CPIMs attempt to forge documents or manipulate personal data, ignoring the official procedures established under existing laws and regulations.

Non-procedural placement of Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) still frequently occurs due to various unmet requirements, such as underage recruitment, lack of competency certification, absence of a work contract, use of non-work visas, placement by unauthorized individuals or P3MI without a valid SIP2MI, and unauthorized job transfers or overstaying due to expired work visas. Yet, if PMIs follow official procedures, they will be registered in the government system, which facilitates access to support and legal protection. Although agencies such as Disperinaker Badung, BP3MI, and the Bali Provincial Government have established effective coordination in PMI supervision and protection, challenges remain on the ground. One key issue is the lack of public understanding in accessing online systems like Sisnaker and Siapkerja, which are actually designed to provide comprehensive information on PMI placement. Findings from this study indicate that the Badung Regency Government does not yet have a specifically designed and scheduled outreach program, largely due to budget limitations. Existing outreach activities are typically conducted only upon instruction from the central or provincial government, with Disperinaker Badung acting solely as an implementing agency within its jurisdiction.

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From the perspective of welfare theory, the government plays an important role in identifying and defining the legal values that exist within society, which are then formulated into regulations through authorized institutions. In addition, the government must also consider the effectiveness and benefits of each regulation it enacts, so that the ultimate goal of public order and societal welfare can be achieved (Isharyanto 2016). The implementation of protection for Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) in Bali Province is a crucial step for the government in promoting public welfare, through improved services and empowerment efforts. As a country that adopts the welfare state concept, Indonesia not only performs administrative functions of governance but also has the obligation to realize social welfare as part of its national goals, achieved through development (Prajudi Atmosudirjo 1994).

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the discussion outlined above, the researcher can draw the following conclusions:

- 1) The PMI placement policy implemented by the Badung Regency Government refers to Bali Governor Regulation No. 12 of 2021 on the Protection System for Krama Bali PMIs, as well as Law No. 18 of 2017 on the Protection of Indonesian Migrant Workers. Badung Regency does not yet have specific regulations concerning PMIs, as Regional Regulation No. 10 of 2021 only governs the general administration of employment services. Therefore, technical services related to PMIs in Badung are carried out based on Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), which cover the issuance of the Job Seeker Card (AK/1), Prospective PMI ID, and passport recommendations for CPMIs.
- 2) Protection for Indonesian Migrant Workers (PMI) from Krama Badung working abroad is implemented in accordance with Bali Governor Regulation No. 12 of 2021 on the Protection System for Krama Bali PMIs. The Badung Regency Government provides protection from the registration stage through to departure, as mandated by Law No. 18 of 2017, which encourages the active role of local governments in managing and protecting PMIs. During employment, protection includes professional services without discrimination, freedom of worship, wages in accordance with the employment contract, access to communication, legal assistance, possession of employment documents, and the right to unionize. After employment, protection is provided through facilitated return to the home region, fulfillment of outstanding rights, assistance for those who are ill or deceased, and PMI empowerment programs. The Badung Regency Government carries out this protection in coordination with the central government and related agencies.

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